

FORMULATION, DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF INJECTION OF POORLY SOLUBLE DRUG (TINIDAZOLE) USING NOVEL APPLICATION OF MIXED SOLVENCY CONCEPT

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ABSTRACT

The objective of present research is the explore the application of mixed solvency technique in the injection formulation of poorly soluble drug and to reduce concentration of individual solubilized (used for solubility enhancement) to minimize the toxic effect of solubilized. the mixed blends in which solubility of tinidazole was more than 1 mg/ml and have much difference in their compositions were selected, such selected mixed blends were FT-5, FT-8 and F-8. To develop 2 ml of aqueous tinidazole injection and constituted dry powder tinidazole injection, the amount of solubilizers and drug that will be administered through each mixed blend was determined. In this case, the solubility agent employed to give a desirable solubility for the poorly soluble drug may produce its own toxicity. However, if the same enhancement in the solubility can be achieved by mixing, five solubilizer (each in one fifth concentration) then the toxicity level of five solubilizer can be reduced by five fold. In case of synergistic effect in solubility due to mixing of, five solubilizer (in the fifth concentration).

These formulation evaluate by UV-visible spectroscopy and IR –Spectroscopy.

KEYWORDS: Solubilized, Injection, Mixed Solvency, Tinidazole, blenzed.

INTRODUCTION

The present investigation was proposed to solubilise tinidazole using combination of various physiologically compatible solubilizers. By increasing the solubility of drug, it might be possible to formulate the small volume parenteral, which will be useful in patient with status epilepticus in which parenteral administration of tinidazole may be required to achieve the required therapeutic plasma concentration rapidly.

OPTIMIZATION OF VARIOUS PARAMETERS FOR AQUEOUS INJECTION FORMULATION OF TINIDAZOLE

Selection of solubilizer blend for injection formulation

On the basis of results obtained from solubility studies, the mixed blends in which solubility of tinidazole was more than 1 mg/ml and have much difference in their compositions were selected, such selected mixed blends were FT-5, FT-8 and F-8. To develop 2 ml of tinidazole injection, the amount of solubilizers and drug that will be administered through each mixed blend was determined.

Table 1.

S. No.	Ingredient	Formula for 52.2 mg/ 2ml	Formula for 50 ml batch
1.	Tinidazole	52.2 mg	1305 mg
2.	Sodium benzoate	0.2 gm	5.0 gm
3.	Ethanol	0.1 ml	2.5 ml
4.	PEG 4000	0.1 gm	2.5 gm
5.	Niacinamide	0.2 gm	5.0 gm

Table 2: Formulation FT-8.

S. No.	Ingredient	Formula for 36 mg/ 2ml	Formula for 50 ml batch
1.	Tinidazole	36.0 mg	900 mg
2.	Sodium benzoate	0.2 gm	5.0 gm
3.	PEG 400	0.1 ml	2.5 ml
4.	Niacinamide	0.2 gm	5 gm
5.	Ethanol	0.1 ml	2.5 ml

FORMULATION OF AQUEOUS INJECTION

Preparation of aqueous solution of tinidazole

Initially, the appropriate weighed amounts (required for 50 ml) of solubilizer were transferred to volumetric flask of 50 ml capacity containing 35 ml sterile water for injection. The flask was shaken to dissolve the solubilizers. The volume was made upto the mark with same

sterile water for injection. To prepare aqueous injection of drug, the calculated quantity of tinidazole was transferred to another flask and prepared blend solution was added to dissolve the drug and shaken for 2 hours to assure complete dissolution of drug. After complete dissolution of drug, volume was made up to the mark with same prepared blend and shaken to get homogenous solution. Other excipients like chelating agent, buffering agent, antioxidants were not added as they may upset the basic solubility enhancement ratio.

Aseptic filtration

Membrane filter 0.22 μm (Millipore) was used for the filtration. The membrane filtration assembly fitted with the membrane filter was sterilized previously in the autoclave at 121°C and 15 lbs pressure for 20 minutes.

DEVELOPMENT OF DRY POWDER INJECTION FORMULATION OF TINIDAZOLE

Powder for injection constitutes an important category of dosage forms for active molecules which are unstable in aqueous media. There are two strategies for the formulation of dry powder injection, first one is lyophilization and second is dry powder filling. A more-stable crystalline stage can be obtained by crystallization in aseptic conditions, and it can be maintained by directly filling the sterile dry-powder drug into presterilized vials mixed with other excipients. The dry-filling process also is much more cost effective because it requires less infrastructures as well as a reduced amount of energy and a shorter amount of time to produce a batch.

SELECTION OF SOLUBILIZER BLEND FOR DRY POWDER INJECTION FORMULATION

On the basis of results obtained from solubility studies in mixed blend containing only solid solubilizer, the mixed blends in which solubility of tinidazole was more than 10 mg/ml and have much difference in their compositions were selected; such blends were F-4, F-5 and F-9. To develop tinidazole dry powder injection, the amount of solubilizers that will be administered through each mixed blend was determined. Injection formulations of various strengths were developed based on solubility of tinidazole in individual blends. The proposed formulations are shown in table.

Table 6: Formulation F-7.

S. No.	Ingredient	Formula for 38.47 mg/ 3ml	Formula for 50 ml batch
1.	Tinidazole	38.47 mg	641 mg
2.	Sodium benzoate	0.3 gm	5.0gm
3.	PEG 6000	0.15 gm	2.5 gm
4.	Urea	0.15 gm	2.5 gm
5.	Niacinamide	0.15 gm	2.5 gm

Table 7: Formulation F-8.

S. No.	Ingredient	Formula for 38.25 mg/ 3ml	Formula for 50 ml batch
1.	Tinidazole	38.47 mg	637 mg
2.	Sodium benzoate	0.3 gm	5.0gm
3.	PEG 6000	0.15 gm	2.5 gm
4.	Urea	0.15 gm	2.5 gm
5.	PEG 4000	0.15 gm	2.5 gm

Table 8: Formulation F-8.

S.No.	Ingredient	Formula for 27mg/ 2ml	Formula for 50 ml batch
1.	Tinidazole	40.5 mg	675 mg
2.	Sodium benzoate	0.3 gm	5.0gm
3.	PVP 40,000	0.15 gm	2.5 gm
4.	PEG 6000	0.15 gm	2.5 gm
5.	Niacinamide	0.15 gm	2.5 gm

FORMULATION OF DRY POWDER INJECTION

Various steps involved in formulation of aqueous injection of tinidazole are as follows:

Treatment of packaging material

Glass vials were first washed three times with distilled water. Finally, these were washed with distilled water, already passed through 0.45 μ m membrane filter. All these vials were dried in an oven and sterilized by dry heating in an oven at 160°C for 2 hours in inverted position.

Rubber closures and aluminium seals used for plugging the vials were first washed several times with distilled water and then autoclaved at 15 lbs pressure (121°C) for 20 minutes and finally dried in oven.

Preparation of aseptic area

The walls and floor of aseptic room were thoroughly washed with filtered tap water followed by 5% phenol solution. The room was fumigated using a mixture of formaldehyde and potassium permanganate.

Preparation of dry powder injection of tinidazole

Initially all the required ingredients of formulation were dried in oven at temperature 40-50 °C. After drying all the ingredients were passed through sieve number 80 to reduce the particle size separately. Then the required quantity of all excipients and drug was weighed and mixed by geometric dilution method with the help of *mortar and pestle aseptically*. The mixed blend was again passed through sieve and mixed manually in plastic bag of suitable size. The mixed powder was then analysed for the uniformity of mixing of drug by taking four samples from the four corners of powder heap. The prepared formulation was then transferred to vials and vials were stoppered and sealed immediately.

EVALUATION OF DRY POWDER INJECTION

Fig. 1.5: Stability of tinidazole in reconstituted product (formulation F-4) at room temperature (RT) and refrigerated condition (RF).

Table 13: Stability of tinidazole in reconstituted product (formulation F-5).

S. No.	Time (hr.)	% Residual drug	
		Refrigerated conditions (2-8°C)	Room temperature
1	0	100.00	100.00
2	2	99.01	98.48
3	4	98.48	96.47
4	6	97.95	95.33
5	8	96.37	95.48
6	10	95.33	93.58

Fig. 1.6: Stability of tinidazole in reconstituted product (formulation F-5) at room temperature (RT) and refrigerated condition (RF).

Table 14: Stability of tinidazole in reconstituted product (formulation F-8).

S. No.	Time (hr.)	% Residual drug	
		Refrigerated conditions (2-8°C)	Room temperature
1	0	100.00	100.00
2	2	99.80	98.6
3	4	99.10	96.78
4	6	99.71	95.39
5	8	99.98	94.00
6	10	98.59	91.15

Fig. 1.6: Stability of tinidazole in reconstituted product (formulation F-8) at room temperature (RT) and refrigerated condition (RF).

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

IDENTIFICATION OF DRUG

Identification by Infrared absorption

Fig 6.1: FTIR spectrum of Tinidazole RS.

Fig 6.1: Infrared spectrum of pure drug (Tinidazole).

Table 17: Interpretation of infrared spectrum of bands of Tinidazole sample.

S.NO.	Wave number (cm-1)	Interpretations
1.	1122.94	C-C single bond stretching
2.	1191.93	Sulfone
3.	1265.22	Strong peak of C-H bending
4.	1390.90	Asymmetric sulfone stretch
5.	1365.51	Tertiary nitrogen
6.	≈1471	Overlapping of C=N & C=C
7.	≈1530	Stretch of NO ₂
8.	2956.67	CH ₃ stretching
9.	3130.25	Aromatic =CH Stretching

Identification by U.V spectrophotometer

According to the Indian Pharmacopoeia the 0.001%w/v solution of Tinidazole in methanol shows absorption maximum at about 310 nm.

Fig 6.2: UV spectrum analysis of tinidazole in methanol by 1700 pharmaSpec Shimadzu UV spectrophotometer.

DETERMINATION OF λ_{max} (MAXIMUM WAVELENGTH)^[25]

The λ_{max} of Tinidazole was determined in distilled water in 1700 pharmaSpec Shimadzu UV spectrophotometer.

- Procedure for the determination of λ_{max}**

10mg of tinidazole was accurately weighed and dissolved in small quantity of methanol in 100ml of volumetric flask and volume was made up to 100ml water was added to produce stock solution having a concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Aliquots of the above solution were taken and diluted to get tinidazole concentration 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The resulting solution was scanned between 200-400 nm on Shimadzu 1700 UV spectrophotometer against distilled water blank. The spectrum is shown in Fig 6.4:-

Fig 6.3 UV spectrum of tinidazole in distilled water by 1700 pharmaSpec Shimadzu UV spectrophotometer.

CALIBRATION CURVE OF TINIDAZOLE

Fig 6.4: Standard curve of tinidazole in distilled water at 318 nm.

Statistical parameters

- Correlation coefficient $r^2 = 0.999$
- Slope = 0.032
- Intercept = 0.001
- Straight line equation = $y = 0.032x + 0.001$

MELTING POINT DETERMINATION

The melting point of the drug was determined by:

- **Melting point apparatus.** The table showing the melting point is given below:

Table 19: Observation of Melting point determination.

Sample no	Melting point($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Average
1	125	126 $^{\circ}\text{C}$
2	126	
3	128	

6.4 HPLC (HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY) ANALYSIS^[26]

Chromatographic conditions

Inject volume- 20 μl

Run time- 0.27 min.

Flow rate- 1 ml/min.

Maximum wavelength- 295 nm.

• HPLC graph of Tinidazole

Figure 6.5: HPLC graph of Tinidazole.

Result and discussion: The observed solubility of lamotrigine in demineralised water was found to be 0.75% w/v (average of three studies).

Fig. 6.5: Solubility profile of lamotrigine in aqueous solution of individual solubilizers (25% w/v).

Results and discussion: It is evident from the results that the solubility of tinidazole was increased by use of various solubilizers. The solubilizing power of different solubilizers could be ranked as Sodium benzoate > Niacinamide > PVP 40,000 > Urea > Tween 20 > PEG 400 > PEG 6000 > PEG 4000 > ethanol.

SOLUBILITY DETERMINATION OF TINIDAZOLE IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION OF MIXED BLEND OF SOLUBILIZERS (25%)

Table 25: Equilibrium solubility data of lamotrigine in various mixed blends containing solubilizers.

Fig. 6.6: Equilibrium solubilities of lamotrigine in various mixed blend containing solubilizers.

Results and discussion: The results showed that solubility of tinidazole in different mixed blends was increased significantly. The maximum solubility was observed in FT-5 which showed 4.59 folds enhancement. From the table 6.6 and 6.7, it is evident that many blends showed additive/synergistic enhancement in solubilities of tinidazole. The total strength of all solubilizers was 25% w/v and 30% w/v in all aqueous systems containing single solubilizers or combinations of solubilizers.

Taking example of blend FT-5, containing (10% Sodium benzoate, 5 Ethanol, PEG 4000, and 10% Niacinamide here. Experimentally observed solubility of tinidazole in this blend was found to be 34.8 mg/ml (Table 6.7)

DETERMINATION OF pH DEPENDENT SOLUBILITY OF TINIDAZOLE

Fig. 6.7: pH dependent solubility profile of lamotrigine.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The solubility of tinidazole slightly increase with increase in pH but it did not vary significantly with pH change. The solubility enhancement ratio at pH 9 was 2.6 folds (as compared to solubility in distilled water).

DRUG-EXCIPIENT INTERACTION STUDIES

Table 26: Drug-excipients physical compatibility study of tinidazole.

S. No.	Drug Excipient Blend	Initial Appearance	Storage conditions												
			Refrigerator(2-8°C)				Room temperature				40°C				
			Week				Week				Week				
			1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	
1.	TNZ	Slight Yellowish white powder	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
2.	TNZ+SB	Slight yellowish white powder	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
3.	TNZ+FH	Slight yellowish white powder	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
4.	TNZ+FT	Slight yellowish white powder	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
5.	TNZ+ST	Slight yellowish white powder	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
6.	TNZ+UR	Slight yellowish white powder	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
7.	TNZ+NM	Slight yellowish white powder	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
8.	TNZ+ET	Slight yellow colour liquid.	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
9.	TNZ+PVP	Slight yellowish white powder	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N

TNZ =Tinidazole FT = PEG 4000

NM =Niacinamide FH = PEG 400

SB =Sodium benzoate ET = Ethanol

PVP =PVP 40,000 ST =PEG 6000

UR = Urea

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